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MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION OF PLASMODIUM STRAINS AND THEIR ASSOCIATION WITH ABO BLOOD GROUPS AND HAEMOGLOBIN LEVELS AMONG FEBRILE PREGNANT WOMEN IN JOS, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Malaria in pregnancy remains a major public health challenge in endemic regions. This study aimed to molecularly detect and characterize Plasmodium strains in febrile pregnant women and assess their correlation with ABO blood groups and hemoglobin levels. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 100 febrile pregnant women attending the antenatal clinic at Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH), Nigeria. Venous blood samples were collected for molecular analysis using a real-time qPCR kit for Plasmodium speciation, ABO blood grouping by the tile method, and hemoglobin estimation

*using a HemoCue analyzer. Data was analyzed using Stata version 17. The overall prevalence of malaria parasitemia by qPCR was 15%. Plasmodium malariae was the most prevalent species (8%), followed by P. falciparum (4%) and P. vivax (3%). No P. Ovale or P. knowlesi were detected. The O-positive blood group was the most common (56%) among participants. There was no statistically significant association between ABO blood groups and overall Plasmodium infection ($p=0.708$) or infection with specific species ($P. falciparum$ $p=0.587$; $P. vivax$ $p=0.657$; $P. malariae$ $p=0.941$). However, a significant association was found between malaria infection and haemoglobin levels ($p=0.034$), with infected participants having lower haemoglobin concentrations. This study reveals a 15% prevalence of malaria among febrile pregnant women in Jos, with *P. malariae* as the predominant species. While ABO blood group was not a significant risk factor for infection, malaria was associated with a higher risk of anemia. These findings underscore the importance of molecular diagnostics for accurate species identification and highlight the need for robust antenatal interventions to prevent malaria and associated anemia in pregnancy.*

KEYWORDS: Malaria in Pregnancy, Plasmodium species, qPCR, ABO Blood Group, Haemoglobin, Jos, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

Malaria infection during pregnancy poses a significant threat to maternal and fetal health, contributing to maternal anemia, low birth weight, preterm delivery, and infant mortality ^[1]. Pregnant women are particularly vulnerable due to pregnancy-induced immunosuppression, especially primigravidae ^[2]. In Nigeria, which bears the highest global burden of malaria, accounting for 27% of cases and 31% of deaths, the impact on pregnant women is profound ^[3].

Plasmodium falciparum infection remains a global public health challenge and is still regarded as a significant parasite cause of morbidity, almost 93% of all global malaria deaths occur in the WHO African region, with Nigeria bearing the highest burden of 19% in 2017 ^[4]. Malaria is caused by the parasite protozoan Plasmodium, which is spread through the bite of an infected female Anopheles mosquito. Parasites go to the liver, where they mature and reproduce ^[5,6]. The disease is caused by Plasmodium parasites dividing in red blood cells, resulting in symptoms such as headache and fever, which can lead to coma and death. The Infection is endemic in tropical and subtropical regions such as Sub-Saharan Africa, Asia, and America ^[5,6].

Previous studies have consistently shown a high prevalence of malaria among pregnant women in Nigeria. For instance, a recent cross-sectional study conducted by Omole et al reported a prevalence rate of 37.28% among pregnant women attending antenatal clinics in Southern Nigeria ^[7]. Similarly, a study found a prevalence rate of 45.38 % among pregnant women attending antenatal at Faith Alive Foundation Hospital, in Jos Nigeria ^[8].

Though humans are infected by five different malaria parasite species, *P. falciparum* is the most common cause of severe sickness in Nigeria, while other species such as *P. ovale*, *P. vivax*, and *P. malariae* are milder and seldom lethal ^[9]. *P. knowlesi* is linked to malaria in macaques and humans (zoonosis). Malaria remains a life-threatening vector-borne disease that has a large economic impact in most endemic areas ^[10,11]. Young children, particularly those under the age of five, pregnant women, and immunocompromised individuals are especially vulnerable ^[12]. Malaria infection during pregnancy is a problem in the tropics and subtropics, affecting approximately 24 million pregnant women ^[13]. The World Health Organization currently suggests that all cases of the parasitic infection must carry out laboratory parasite-based test before therapy due to inadequate data on the effectiveness of presumptive tests ^[14].

The haematological changes in malaria, particularly anemia, are well-documented. The ABO blood group system has also been investigated as a potential factor influencing susceptibility to severe malaria, with some studies suggesting a protective effect for blood group O^[15, 16]. However, findings are inconsistent, and data specific to pregnant women and correlation with circulating Plasmodium species are limited.

Diagnostic challenges further complicated management. Microscopy and Rapid Diagnostic Tests (RDTs), while widely used, have limitations in sensitivity and species differentiation, especially at low parasitemia common in semi-immune individuals^[17]. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) offers a more sensitive and specific method for detecting and characterizing Plasmodium species.

This study aimed to bridge the knowledge gap by using molecular techniques to determine the prevalence and distribution of Plasmodium species in febrile pregnant women in Jos University Teaching Hospital, Nigeria, and to evaluate their correlation with ABO blood groups and haemoglobin levels.

METHODOLOGY

- **Study Design and Area**

A cross-sectional study was conducted at the Antenatal Clinic of Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH) and the Genomics and Postgraduate Research Laboratory, University of Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.

- **Study Population and Sampling**

The study population consisted of pregnant women attending antenatal care at JUTH. Using Fisher's formula with a prevalence (p) of 8.5%. A 95% confidence level ($Z=1.96$), and a margin of error (d) of 5%, a minimum sample size of 120 was calculated. A total of 100 participants were eventually enrolled. Ethical approval was obtained from the JUTH Health Research Ethics Committee (NHREC/JUTH/05/01/22), and informed consent was secured from all participants.

- **Data and Sample Collection**

A structured questionnaire was used to collect demographic and clinical data. Venous blood (5 ml) was collected from each participant into K2 EDTA tubes.

- **Extraction and quantification of genomic DNA**

The extraction and quantification of the DNA from the whole blood sample were performed using DNeasy Blood & Tissue Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany), following the manufacturer's protocol. The extracted DNA was quantified using a Qubit 4 Fluorometer

- **Detection of plasmodium's genotypes using the real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR)**

For each DNA sample, malaria differentiations were performed using VIASURE *real-time polymerase chain reaction (qPCR)* kit (CerTest, Spain). Briefly, each PCR reaction was reconstituted according to the number of PCR wells and samples, performed in a 20- μ l reaction volume consisting of 5 μ l aliquot of DNA added to VIASURE PCR Mix (15 μ l aliquot for each

mixture) on a CFX96 Real-time PCR system (Bio-Rad Laboratories, Inc., Hercules, CA, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The thermal cycler conditions consisted of an initial polymerase activation at 95 °C for 2 min, denaturation at 95 °C for 10 seconds, followed by 45 cycles of annealing, extension and data acquisition at 60 °C for 50 seconds targeting the conserved region of the Rrna18S gene.

DNA Extraction and PCR: Genomic DNA was extracted from whole blood using a commercial kit. Molecular detection and differentiation of Plasmodium species (*P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. malariae*, *P. ovale*, *P. knowlesi*) were performed using the Viasure Malaria Differentiation Real-Time PCR Detection Kit, targeting the 18S rRNA gene.

- **ABO and Rh Blood Grouping**

The ABO blood group of each subject was determined using cell grouping Antisera as by Rosenfield [22] and Cheesbrough [23]. Monoclonal Antisera A, B, and D (Agappe Diagnostics Ltd, India) were used for the assay.

Haemoglobin Estimation: Measured using a HemoCue Hb 201 analyzer.

- **Statistical Analysis**

Data was analyzed using Stata version 17. Descriptive statistics were presented as frequencies and percentages. The Chi-square test was used to determine associations between categorical variables. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- **Demographic Characteristics**

Most participants were aged 26-35 years (57%). Over half (57.6%) were in their second trimester, 26.3% in the third, and 16.2% in the first trimester. The O-positive blood group was predominant (56%), followed by A-positive (23%). Most participants had hemoglobin levels of 11 g/dL (31.3%) or 12 g/dL (41.4%). A high proportion reported using insecticide-treated nets (68%), and 54% had taken antimalarial drugs (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Study Population (n=100)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age Group	15-20	8.0	8.0
	21-25	25.0	25.0
	26-30	28.0	28.0
	31-35	29.0	29.0
	36-40	10.0	10.0
Trimester	First	16.0	16.0
	Second	58.0	58.0
	Third	26.0	26.0
Blood Group	A+	23.0	23.0
	A-	3.0	3.0
	B+	13	13
	O+	56.0	56.0
	O-	5.0	5.0
Mosquito Net	Yes	68.0	68.0
	No	32.0	32.0
Antimalaria Drug	Yes	54.0	54.0
	No	46.0	56.0

- Prevalence and Distribution of Plasmodium Species**

The overall prevalence of Plasmodium infection was 15% (15/100). Among the positive cases, *P. malariae* was the most frequently detected species (8%), followed by *P. falciparum* (4%) and *P. vivax* (3%). No cases of *P. ovale* or *P. knowlesi* were identified (Table 2).

Table 2: Prevalence of Plasmodium Species by qPCR (n=100)

Plasmodium Species	Negative (%)	Positive (%)
Any species	85(85.0)	15(15.0)
<i>P. falciparum</i>	96(96.0)	4(4.0)
<i>P. vivax</i>	97(97.0)	3(3.0)
<i>P. malariae</i>	92(92.0)	8(8.0)
<i>P. ovale</i>	100(100)	0(0.0)
<i>P. knowlesi</i>	100(100)	0(0.0)

- **Figure 1; Overall Prevalence of Plasmodium**

- **Figure 2; Prevalence of infection by Plasmodium species**

- **Association between Malaria, ABO Blood Groups, and Hemoglobin**

There was no statistically significant association between ABO blood groups and the prevalence of overall malaria infection ($p=0.708$) or infection with specific species (*P. falciparum* $p=0.587$; *P. vivax* $p=0.657$; *P. malariae* $p=0.941$) (Table 3).

Table 3: Association between Plasmodium Infection and ABO Blood Group

Blood Group	Plasmodium Negative	Plasmodium Positive	Total	P-value
A+	19	4	23	
A-	3	0	3	
B+	12	1	13	0.708
O+	46	10	56	
O-	5	0	5	
Total	85	15	100	

A significant association was observed between malaria infection status and haemoglobin levels ($p=0.034$). Infected participants were more likely to have lower hemoglobin levels (10-12 g/dL) compared to non-infected participants (Table 4).

Table 4: Association between Plasmodium Infection and Haemoglobin Level

Haemoglobin (g/dL)	Plasmodium Negative(n=86)	Plasmodium Positive(n=14)	P-value
10	3	2	
11	27	4	
12	40	2	0.034
13	13	6	
14	2	0	
15	1	0	

This study provides important insights into the molecular epidemiology of malaria in febrile pregnant women in north-central Nigeria. The overall malaria prevalence of 15% detected by qPCR is lower than rates often reported in Nigerian studies using microscopy, which may reflect the specific study population, the high usage of mosquito nets (68%), or the superior specificity of qPCR in febrile illness diagnosis, correctly identifying true *Plasmodium* infections.

A key finding is the predominance of *P. malariae* (8%), surpassing *P. falciparum* (4%). This is unusual, as *P. falciparum* is typically responsible for over 95% of malaria cases in Nigeria [3]. This finding suggests a possible unique transmission dynamic in the study area or in the pregnant population, where *P. malariae*, known for causing chronic infections with low, persistent

parasitemia, might be underreported by less sensitive methods. The detection of vivax (3%) is also notable, given the high prevalence of Duffy-negative phenotype in West Africa, which traditionally confers resistance to this species. This indicates that *P. vivax* is present and should not be overlooked in diagnostic and treatment algorithms.

We found no significant association between ABO blood groups and susceptibility to malaria infection or infection with specific species. This suggests that in this population, ABO blood group may not be a major determinant of infection risk.

The significant association between malaria infection and lower haemoglobin levels ($p=0.034$) reinforces the established link between malaria and anemia in pregnancy. Malaria contributes to anemia through hemolysis of infected red blood cells, increased splenic clearance, and dyserythropoiesis. This finding underscores the critical need to integrate effective malaria prevention and treatment into antenatal care to mitigate one of its most common and detrimental consequences.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the utility of molecular diagnostics in revealing the complex epidemiology of malaria in pregnancy. The unexpected predominance of *P. malariae* and the presence of *P. vivax* highlight the need for species-specific diagnostics to guide appropriate treatment, particularly with the hypnozoitocidal therapy required for *P. vivax*. The significant association with anemia confirms the importance of malaria as a cause of maternal morbidity. Public health efforts should continue to promote the use of insecticide-treated nets and intermittent preventive treatment in pregnancy (IPTp) to reduce the burden of malaria and its complications in this vulnerable group.

- **Limitations:** The sample size, though calculated, may limit the power to detect weaker associations, particularly for less prevalent species. The study was conducted in a single tertiary hospital, which may affect the generalizability of the findings.
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- **Conflict of interest Statement**

The authors have no competing interest to declare.

- **Consent for publication**

All participant provided informed consent for publication of research findings as summary with no identifiable personal information.

- **Ethics approval**

The research protocol for this study with informed consent for the enrolment procedures were reviewed and approved by the Jos University Teaching Hospital's Health and Research Ethics Committee. The approval reference for the research protocol is: **NHREC/JUTH/05/01/22**. All

participants signed an informed consent for all enrolment procedures which were conducted in accordance with the relevant regulatory guidelines as in the Helsinki's declaration.

- **Data Availability**

All the relevant data for this analysis have been presented in body of this manuscript and the associated tables.

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